

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, Alison K. Post, and R. Chelsea Nagy

Patagonian Plankton Swirls
(Credit: [NASA Image of the Day](#))

Quick Updates

- Several new papers were published by Earth Lab members, including "[The invasive plant data landscape: a synthesis of spatial data and applications for research and management in the United States](#)" by a team including Adam Mahood, and Chelsea Nagy.
- A new USGS report led by the North Central Climate Adaptation Science Center (NC CASC), "[Synthesis of Climate and Ecological Science to Support Grassland Management Priorities in the North Central Region](#)" by Christine D. Miller Hessed, Heather M. Yocum, Imtiaz Rangwala, Chelsea Nagy & others.
- Earth lab's EDS Seminar series held numerous talks and interactive workshops this quarter. Visit our [blog](#) & [youtube channel](#) to learn more.
 - Earth Lab's Ty Tuff gave a seminar about the technical details and potential of ChatGPT
 - Ulyana Peña of the NC CASC gave a seminar about "The Art of Science Storytelling"
 - Earth Lab's Education team held a training about reproducible workflows in Github

Open House

On April 4th, Earth Lab hosted a half-day open house to showcase Earth Lab research and resources to the broader university community, as well as foster new collaborations with researchers across diverse CU departments and external agencies (NOAA, NCAR, NEON).

About 65 people attended (50 in-person, 15 virtually), representing 17 CU Boulder departments/programs and 7 external agencies.

The event included a series of 25 2-minute flash talks, as well as dedicated networking time for attendees to connect and discuss potential collaborations. Through this event, Earth Lab established several promising partnerships that we anticipate will develop into new collaborative proposals and projects.

New Team Member Q & A

**Lilly Jones,
Postdoctoral Associate**

1. What is your background?

I completed a PhD in Geology and Geology Engineering and a graduate certificate in geospatial technology at SD School of Mines. Most recently I was an adjunct instructor at Oglala Lakota College on the Pine Ridge Reservation in South Dakota, where I also earned my BS in Environmental and Earth Sciences. My interests include hydrogeology, geomorphology, environmental risk modeling, and data science.

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

I am looking forward to collaborating with top research scientists from several disciplines on a cutting-edge project that has practical implications for front-line communities.

3. What is your favorite national park

Badlands NP, which is included in the study area for my dissertation.

Macrosystems Workshop

In February, Earth Lab hosted the **Forest Resiliency Data Synthesis Working Group** for a 4-day in-person event. Thirty-two participants attended from across the United States and Mexico, representing a wide variety of career stages, disciplines, and both academic and non-academic institutions. The working group followed a blended model of a data training institute and a synthesis working group with the following objectives:

1. Increasing participants' data skills, networking, and synthesis science capabilities
2. Incubating ideas and facilitating data-driven inquiry leading to team-driven synthesis products
3. Training participants in data- and compute-intensive workflows for forest resiliency research

Attendees participated in educational modules hosted on a deployed cyberinfrastructure platform enabling data sharing and cloud computing. Facilitated working group sessions emphasized data-inspired subject-relevant synthesis, and many of the groups have continued to meet after the event with the intent to publish collaborative scientific papers.

Read more in the Earth Lab [blog](#) post by Tyler McIntosh!

Earth Data Analytics Professional Graduate Certificate

Apply today for Earth Lab's [Earth Data Analytics Professional Graduate Certificate](#), hosted by the University of Colorado Boulder! You'll learn the fundamental scientific programming and data science skills to launch your career in earth data science. The certificate includes three courses (nine credits) and a capstone project with an industry partner or other agency such as World Wildlife Fund, Google, or USGS. [Apply online](#) by August 8th!

VIRTUAL INFO SESSION

If you're interested in the certificate but not sure if it's right for you, join us on July 12th at 4pm MDT for a Virtual Information Session!

**JULY
12th**

4:00-5:00pm MT

Earth Lab's Education Team will be there to answer any questions you may have about the program, application, or field. Hope to see you there! [Register](#) for the info session [here](#).

Social Media

Earth Lab social media is growing! In February, Earth Lab joined Instagram, expanding our existing social media presence. Find us on Twitter, LinkedIn, and now Instagram!

@earthlabcu